

The risk of unfavorable pregnancy outcomes in women who are obese

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To study the association between maternal overweight and complications during pregnancy and childbirth. In Asian countries, the prevalence of obesity among women with children is increasing, which is of great importance for obstetrics. The objective of this study was to examine the prevalence of overweight and obese mothers from the first to mid-trimester trimesters and their effects on maternal, perinatal and neonatal outcomes. Secondary data collected from single pregnancies were analyzed and these were included in an Asian co-operation study on antioxidant vitamin C and vitamin E supplementation to prevent preeclampsia in women. Pregnant the women were categorized into three groups based on body mass index (BMI): normal (BMI 18.5-24.9 kg / m²), overweight (BMI 25-29.9 kg / m²) and obesity (BMI. 30-34.9 kg / m²) Obstetrics and perinatal results were compared through single factor and multifactor analysis. Women who are overweight and obese have an increased risk of pregnancy and childbirth. The likelihood of having these symptoms increases with the increase in body mass index. Healthcare professionals should be empowered and trained to provide promising nutritional and lifestyle interventions for women at risk of pre-pregnancy overweight and obesity, and to control their increases. Excessive weight during pregnancy

Keywords: *obesity, prior to conception, pregnancy, vitamin C, E BMI.*

Introduction

A high BMI during pregnancy increases the risk of many pregnancy complications, including the risk of miscarriages, stillbirths and miscarriages. Diabetes disease while pregnant. In Australia, the incidence of being overweight and obesity increased among men and women and of all age groups between 2014 and 2015, approximately 15% of women aged 25-34 were obese [1]. Therefore, pregnant women who are overweight and obese are critical in providing obstetric care as measured by an increase in the maternal body mass index (BMI). Being obese during pregnancy and childbirth has a significant risk of prenatal complications, postpartum and neonatal. Prenatal complications include recurrent miscarriages, congenital anomalies, pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH), preeclampsia, gestational diabetes (GDM), and venous thromboembolism [2-5] Women who are overweight and obese are more likely to be motivated and need a caesarean section. [6,7] Babies with overweight and

obese mothers are often large and require hospitalization. [6,7] It is estimated that, based on the degree of obesity, the cost of overweight women perinatal health is 5.4 to 16.2 times higher than the normal weight control group [2]. Children with greater gestational age (LFGA) at birth may be at risk of diabetes or obesity in the intrauterine environment, and the risk of metabolic syndrome increases, which in turn contributes to the obesity and obesity life cycle. For a long time Insulin resistance in offspring [3] This study aimed to assess the prevalence and influence of overweight and obese mothers in a sample of non-pregnant women from early to mid-term on outcomes of infant mothers. Perinatal and neonatal another objective is to define maternal traits associated with a high risk of being overweight and obesity.

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Background

A 2000 woman participated in the Antioxidant Vitamin C and Vitamin E trial to prevent preeclampsia in pregnant women. This is a multi-center, placebo-controlled trial to prevent complications. [4]. The study recruited non-pregnant women with a single pregnancy between 14 and 22 weeks of gestation and their blood pressure returned to normal at the time of the measurement. First pregnancy and getting into the test among these women, 1784 (88%) recorded the BMI on the first prenatal test and was included in this study. The admissions study period was December 2014 through January 2019. The women were randomly divided into either a vitamin group (100 mg vitamin C and 400 mg vitamin E per day) or a placebo group. (Four cellulose microcrystalline tablets per day) through a randomized service via central telephone. The main results of this trial were previously published [5]. The experiments found no overall differences in the perinatal results between the antioxidant and vitamin groups, so data from both groups was included with the study. Analysis of current studies According to the female body mass index (BMI), women fall into three categories.

From the hospital data for the first antenatal care, it was calculated that it was normal. (BMI 18.5-24.9 kg / sq m), overweight (BMI 25-29.9 kg / sq m) and obesity (BMI greater than 30 kg / sq m). .)

Data Collection and outcome variables

Social demographic variables were gathered from women's medical records or a self-filled questionnaire. These variables were pregnant woman's age, race, body mass index, socioeconomic status, and measured by the socioeconomic area index (SEIFA) score [6], Maternal education at school, smoking and blood pressure. The pregnancy outcomes that were evaluated included: adverse maternal outcomes. (The accompanying results were defined as one of the following six weeks before birth: mortality, pulmonary edema, preeclampsia, stroke, thrombocytopenia, renal failure, apnea, Placental abruption, abnormal liver function, threatened miscarriage Cystic fibrosis, severe postpartum hemorrhage, fever after birth, pneumonia, deep vein thrombosis or pulmonary embolism requiring anticoagulant therapy); Pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH); Preeclampsia (Defined as systolic blood pressure $\geq$ 140 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure $\geq$ 90 mm Hg, at least four hours apart, or both after 20 weeks of gestation and occurring. One or more of the following: proteinuria, kidney failure, liver disease, neuropathy, blood system disease, or fetal growth restriction) [7]; Prenatal hospitalization, premature rupture of membranes to induce labor, delivery methods, postpartum complications such as postpartum hemorrhage and infection, and length of stay. Neonatal outcomes include the sum of death or adverse fetal outcomes, defined as fetal or perinatal death, birth weight <gestational age <3%, respiratory syndrome. Severe cystic fibrosis, grade 3 or 4, abdominal hemorrhage, abdominal lung disease. Embryo cells, Grade 3 or 4 premature, Necrotosis, 5 min. Apgar score <4, Onset 24h prior or need control of 2 or more drugs, hypotonia $\geq$ 2 h, stupor, Yes, pain or weaker coma response, tube feeding $\geq$ 4 days, neonatal care (NICU) for > 4 days, or ventilation $\geq$ 24 hours [13,14], and : Gestational age; Premature birth (<37 weeks); 5 minutes Apgar score <7; The shape of the baby at birth (Weight, length and head circumference), low gestational age and very gestational age (According to the following definition, birth weight is less than 10% or more than 90%)

The fetal sex was performed according to the respective birth weight chart [8] the giant baby. (Birth weight $\geq$ 4.5 kg), admission to the neonatal nurses or nursery, dyspnea and length of stay

Statistical Analysis

Use SAS software version 9.1 for statistical analysis. The binomial regression log is used in the analysis of binary variables, and the results are expressed as relative risk and 95% confidence intervals. If continuous variables are normally distributed, variance analysis is used to analyze them and express them as differences. The risk-adjusted mean with 95% confidence intervals. The non-parametric test was used for distorted data. The $p < 0.05$ was statistically significant. The women group with normal BMI was used as the reference category for all analyzes.

Results

Demographic data from 1661 women included in the study, 943 (57%) had a normal BMI on the first prenatal health check, 446 (27%) were overweight and 272 (16%) were obese (table. 1) None of the women had a BMI lower than 18.5 among all three groups. The median gestational age in the trial was 17.2 weeks, compared with women with a normal BMI. Significant higher systolic blood pressure readings were observed when participating in the trial. (Mean Difference (MD) 3.6 [95% CI 2.5, 4.8], $p < 0.0001$ and MD 7.8 [95% CI 6.4,9.2], $p < 0.0001$). Similar findings were found in the readings. Diastolic blood pressure values at the beginning of the trial (MD 2.5 [95% CI 1.6, 3.4], $p < 0.0001$ and MD 6.1 [95% CI 5.1, 7.2], $p < 0.0001$, respectively). (Table 1). Compared to normal-weight women, overweight women were less likely to be white and less likely to be Asian (RR 1.03 [95% CI 1.00, 1.05], $p = 0.03$ and RR 0.33 [95% CI 0.14, 0.78], $p = 0.01$) Obese women were less Asian than women with normal BMI (RR 0.36 [95% CI 0.13, 1.01], $p = 0.05$) (Table No. 1) Compared to normal-weight women, overweight and obese women were more likely to receive TAFE or equivalent (RR 1.26 [95% CI 1.03, 1.53], $p = 0.02$, and RR 1.32 [95% CI 1.06, 1.66], $p = 0.01$). Obese women were less likely to go to college than women with normal weight (RR 0.71 [95% CI 0.57, 0.89], $p = 0.003$). Normal BMI, obese women are more likely to live At a lower socioeconomic level (RR 1.50 [95% CI 1.23, 1.83], $p = 0.0001$), therefore, compared to women with a normal BMI, obese women tended to have socioeconomic levels at the lower socioeconomic level (RR 1.50 [95% CI 1.23, 1.83], $p = 0.0001$). Higher (RR 0.67 (95% CI 0.52, 0.84), $p = 0.001$).

Table 1. Demographics of women with normal BMI compared with overweight and obese women

Characteristic	Normal n = 943 (%)	Overweight n = 446 (%)	Obese n = 272 (%)	Overweight vs. Normal [95% CI]	p value	Obese vs. Normal [95% CI]	p value
Age (years) ^a	26.7 $\pm$ 5.9	26.8 $\pm$ 5.6	26.4 $\pm$ 5.1	0.2 [-0.5,0.8]	0.61	-0.3 [-1.1,0.5]	0.44
GA Entry (weeks) ^a	17.2 $\pm$ 2.4	17.2 $\pm$ 2.4	17.2 $\pm$ 2.5	-0.04 [-0.3,0.2]	0.77	-0.05 [-0.4,0.3]	0.77
Systolic BP at Trial Entry (mm Hg) ^a	108.2 $\pm$ 10.2	111.8 $\pm$ 9.9	116.0 $\pm$ 9.7	3.6 [2.5,4.8]	< 0.0001	7.8 [6.4,9.2]	< 0.0001
Diastolic BP at Trial Entry (mm Hg) ^a	63.8 $\pm$ 7.6	66.3 $\pm$ 7.9	70.0 $\pm$ 7.8	2.5 [1.6,3.4]	< 0.0001	6.1 [5.1,7.2]	< 0.0001
Race							
Caucasian	885 (93.8)	430 (96.4)	261 (96.0)	1.03 [1.00,1.05]	0.03	1.02 [0.99,1.05]	0.14

Asian	38 (4.0)	6 (1.3)	4 (1.5)	0.33	[0.14,0.78]	0.01	0.36	[0.13,1.01]	0.05
Other	20 (2.1)	10 (2.2)	7 (2.6)	1.06	[0.50,2.24]	0.88	1.21	[0.52,2.84]	0.66
Education									
Secondary or lower	394 (42.8)	182 (41.8)	124 (46.1)	0.98	[0.86,1.12]	0.74	1.08	[0.93,1.25]	0.33
Diploma or equiv	199 (21.6)	118 (27.1)	77 (28.6)	1.26	[1.03,1.53]	0.02	1.32	[1.06,1.66]	0.01
University	328 (35.6)	135 (31.0)	68 (25.3)	0.87	[0.74,1.03]	0.10	0.71	[0.57,0.89]	0.003
Socio-economic index									
Low SEI	222 (23.5)	112 (25.1)	96 (35.3)	1.07	[0.88,1.30]	0.52	1.50	[1.23,1.83]	0.0001
Low-Mid SEI	155 (16.4)	81 (18.2)	44 (16.2)	1.10	[0.87,1.41]	0.42	0.98	[0.72,1.34]	0.92
Mid-High SEI	248 (26.3)	119 (26.7)	71 (26.1)	1.01	[0.84,1.22]	0.88	0.99	[0.79,1.25]	0.95
High SEI	318 (33.7)	134 (30.0)	61 (22.4)	0.89	[0.75,1.05]	0.18	0.67	[0.52,0.84]	0.001
Smoking	198 (21.0)	94 (21.1)	51 (18.8)	1.00	[0.81,1.25]	0.97	0.89	[0.68,1.18]	0.42
Characteristic	Normal n = 943 (%)	Overweight n = 446 (%)	Obese n = 272 (%)	Overweight vs. Normal [95% CI]		p value	Obese vs. Normal [95% CI]		p value
Age (years) ^a	26.7 ± 5.9	26.8 ± 5.6	26.4 ± 5.1	0.2	[-0.5,0.8]	0.61	-0.3	[-1.1,0.5]	0.44
GA Entry (weeks) ^a	17.2 ± 2.4	17.2 ± 2.4	17.2 ± 2.5	-0.04	[-0.3,0.2]	0.77	-0.05	[-0.4,0.3]	0.77
Systolic BP at Trial Entry (mm Hg) ^a	108.2 ± 10.2	111.8 ± 9.9	116.0 ± 9.7	3.6	[2.5,4.8]	< 0.0001	7.8	[6.4,9.2]	< 0.0001
Diastolic BP at Trial Entry (mm Hg) ^a	63.8 ± 7.6	66.3 ± 7.9	70.0 ± 7.8	2.5	[1.6,3.4]	< 0.0001	6.1	[5.1,7.2]	< 0.0001
Race									
Caucasian	885 (93.8)	430 (96.4)	261 (96.0)	1.03	[1.00,1.05]	0.03	1.02	[0.99,1.05]	0.14
Asian	38 (4.0)	6 (1.3)	4 (1.5)	0.33	[0.14,0.78]	0.01	0.36	[0.13,1.01]	0.05
Other	20 (2.1)	10 (2.2)	7 (2.6)	1.06	[0.50,2.24]	0.88	1.21	[0.52,2.84]	0.66
Education									
Secondary or lower	394 (42.8)	182 (41.8)	124 (46.1)	0.98	[0.86,1.12]	0.74	1.08	[0.93,1.25]	0.33
Diploma or equiv	199 (21.6)	118 (27.1)	77 (28.6)	1.26	[1.03,1.53]	0.02	1.32	[1.06,1.66]	0.01
University	328 (35.6)	135 (31.0)	68 (25.3)	0.87	[0.74,1.03]	0.10	0.71	[0.57,0.89]	0.003
Socio-economic index									
Low SEI	222 (23.5)	112 (25.1)	96 (35.3)	1.07	[0.88,1.30]	0.52	1.50	[1.23,1.83]	0.0001
Low-Mid SEI	155 (16.4)	81 (18.2)	44 (16.2)	1.10	[0.87,1.41]	0.42	0.98	[0.72,1.34]	0.92
Mid-High SEI	248 (26.3)	119 (26.7)	71 (26.1)	1.01	[0.84,1.22]	0.88	0.99	[0.79,1.25]	0.95
High SEI	318 (33.7)	134 (30.0)	61 (22.4)	0.89	[0.75,1.05]	0.18	0.67	[0.52,0.84]	0.001
Smoking	198 (21.0)	94 (21.1)	51 (18.8)	1.00	[0.81,1.25]	0.97	0.89	[0.68,1.18]	0.42

Pregnancy Outcomes

Obese women were at higher risk of developing preeclampsia compared with women with a normal BMI (RR 2.99 [95%CI 1.88, 4.73], $p < 0.0001$). They were more likely to be hospitalized for hypertension than women with a normal BMI (RR 2.87 [95%CI 1.70, 4.84], $p = 0.0001$) (Table 2). Obese women received more magnesium sulphate and antihypertensive than women with a normal BMI (RR 2.97 [95%CI 1.01, 8.77], $p = 0.05$ and RR 3.31 [95%CI 1.85, 5.93], $p = 0.0001$ respectively) (Table 2). Compared to women with a normal BMI, overweight and obese women had an increased risk of pregnancy induced hypertension (PIH) than women with a

Normal BMI (RR 1.94 [95%CI 1.43, 2.65], $p < 0.0001$ and RR 3.19 [95%CI 2.36, 4.30], $p < 0.0001$ respectively) and severe PIH (RR 2.76 [95%CI 1.35, 5.64], $p = 0.01$ and RR 4.00 [95%CI 1.93, 8.30], $p = 0.0002$ respectively) (Table 2). Obese women were at higher risk of developing gestational diabetes than women with a normal BMI (RR 2.10 [95%CI 1.17, 3.79], $p = 0.01$). Relating to induction of labor, overweight and obese women were more likely to be induced than women with a normal BMI (RR 1.33 [95%CI 1.13, 1.57], $p = 0.001$ and RR 1.78 [95%CI 1.51, 2.09], $p < 0.0001$ respectively).

Table 2. Pregnancy complications among women with normal BMI compared with overweight and obese women

Characteristic	Normal	Overweight	Obese	Overweight	p value	Obese	p value
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	n = 943 (%)	n = 446 (%)	n = 272 (%)	vs. Normal [95% CI]	vs. Normal [95% CI]	vs. Normal [95% CI]
Maternal Death or Adverse Outcome	68 (7.2)	43 (9.6)	28 (10.3)	1.34 [0.93,1.93]	0.12	1.43 [0.94,2.17] 0.10
Pre-Eclampsia	36 (3.8)	25 (5.6)	31 (11.4)	1.47 [0.89,2.42]	0.13	2.99 [1.88,4.73] < 0.0001
Pregnancy Induced Hypertension	74 (7.8)	68 (15.2)	68 (25.0)	1.94 [1.43,2.65]	< 0.0001	3.19 [2.36,4.30] < 0.0001
Severe PIH	13 (1.4)	17 (3.8)	15 (5.5)	2.76 [1.35,5.64]	0.01	4.00 [1.93,8.30] 0.0002
Antenatal hospitalization hypertension	29 (3.1)	19 (4.3)	24 (8.8)	1.39 [0.79,2.44]	0.26	2.87 [1.70,4.84] 0.0001
MgSO4 used	7 (0.7)	4 (0.9)	6 (2.2)	1.21 [0.36,4.11]	0.76	2.97 [1.01,8.77] 0.05
2 hr OGTT ≥ 7.8 mmol/L	28 (3.0)	16 (3.6)	17 (6.3)	1.21 [0.66,2.21]	0.54	2.10 [1.17,3.79] 0.01
Antihypertensive	22 (2.3)	17 (3.8)	21 (7.7)	1.63 [0.88,3.05]	0.12	3.31 [1.85,5.93] 0.0001
PPROM	23 (2.4)	16 (3.6)	8 (2.9)	1.47 [0.78,2.76]	0.23	1.21 [0.55,2.67] 0.64

Compared to women with normal BMI, hypertension was more common among overweight and obese women (RR 1.93 [95% CI 1.21, 3.08], $p = 0.01$ and RR 3.96 [95% CI 2.57, 6.11], $p < 0.0001$). Compared with women with normal BMI, overweight and obese women were more likely to develop diabetes-related complications (RR 4.93 [95% CI 1.28, 18.99], $p = 0.02$, and RR 11.6 [95% CI 3.20, 41.69], $p = 0.0002$) compared to women with normal BMI. Emergency caesarean section (RR 1.42 [95% CI 1.18, 1.70], $p = 0.0002$ and RR 1.63 [95% CI 1.34, 1.99] $p < 0.0001$, respectively (RR 1.48 [95% CI 1.19, 1.83], $p = 0.0004$ and 1.77 [95% CI 1.40, 2.23], $p < 0.0001$) (Table 3) for indications for caesarean section. Body mass index than Aura. Many women require a C-section for preeclampsia (RR 3.47 [95% CI 1.39, 8.65], $p = 0.01$). Overweight and obese women are more likely to have a C-section. Normal body mass (RR 1.40 [95% CI 1.03, 1.91], $p = 0.03$ and RR 1.71 [95% CI 1.23, 2.40], $p = 0.002$) and overweight and obese women who needed a caesarean section. This is because fetal distress is more likely to suffer a caesarean failure than women who have. High normal BMI (RR 1.50 [95% CI 1.10, 2.06], $p = 0.01$ and RR 1.84 [95% CI 1.31, 2.58], $p = 0.0004$) (Table 3) compared to women with index normal body mass. Overweight women require more antibiotic treatment after delivery (RR 1.30 [95% CI 1.01, 1.67], $p = 0.04$). Obese women are more likely to need antibiotics to treat their infection. The wounded infections were greater than women with normal BMI (RR 2.77 [95% CI 1.11, 6.96], $p = 0.03$).

The average birth weight of infants born to obese and obese mothers was higher than those born to women with a normal BMI (MD 64.4 (95% CI -0.9, 129.8), $p = 0.05$ and MD 99.7 [95% CI 21.3, 178.2], p equal to 0.01) (Table 4) Zscore. The birth weight of infants born to overweight and obese mothers was higher than those born to those born to obese mothers. The normal BMI was statistically significant (MD 0.10 [95% CI -0.00, 0.21], $P = 0.06$ and

MD 0.24 [95% CI 0.11, 0.37, respectively], $p = 0.0003$). 4). Infants of obese mothers were more likely to be pregnant (LFGA) BMI (RR 2.08 [95% CI 1.47, 2.93], $p < 0.0001$) (Table 4). The total number of mothers was greater than the average (RR 4.54 [95% CI 2.01, 10.24], $p = 0.0003$) (Table 4). Infants of mothers with normal BMIs, overweight infants, and obese mothers had larger head circumference (MD 0.30 [95% CI 0.1, 0.5], $p = 0.01$ and MD 0.34 [95% CI 0.1, 0.6], $p = 0.01$) (Table 4), so this finding is similar to the newborn head circumference Z score (MD 0.18 [95% CI 0.05, 0.31], $p = 0.01$ and MD 0.28 [95% CI 0.13, 0.44], $p = 0.0003$)

Discussion

Our research found that increases in the BMI of pregnant women were associated with negative effects on maternal and infant health. The findings are consistent with previous studies, suggesting that there is an increased association between increased pregnant women's BMI and pregnancy-induced hypertension, GDM, stimulation. In this regard, the prevalence of being overweight and obesity in pregnant women (43 %) Found that it was higher than another study in Asian women maternity in Queensland from 1998 to 2002 which reported that 34% of women were overweight or obese [9]. Therefore, the higher prevalence in this study was consistent with national data showing that the Asian population is overweight and obese [10]. More likely to be overweight and obese than Asian women. The relationship between increased BMI and associated complications varies with race. For any BMI, Asian populations have more fat and joint disease, leading to different BMI criteria for these populations [11]. We use the same BMI scores for all competitions included in our study, and as a result, Asian women were more likely to be allocated in the normal BMI category. Obese were more likely to receive a TAFE degree or equivalent than women of normal weight.

Obese women were less likely to get a college education than women who were at a healthy weight. In addition, compared to women in the BMI group, obese women typically had lower socioeconomic levels^[13]. This was consistent with the results of a large population-based study in Australia. Lower obesity is always a sign of obesity for men and women, and increasing income reduces the risk of obesity in women^[14]. Our study confirms the association between increased BMI and risk of obesity. PIH [4,6,7,18,19] Although obese women have an increased risk of preeclampsia compared to women of normal weight. But we have yet to find any difference between overweight and normal weight people. However, those who are overweight tend to increase the risk^[15]. Previous studies have shown that there is a linear relationship between increased BMI in overweight and obese women and hypothyroidism. Preeclampsia, which is more pronounced than in women who have not given birth [16] It is estimated that for every 1 unit of BMI in non-pregnant women, the risk of preeclampsia increases by 7% (95% CI 1.06, 1.08) and risk of preeclampsia increased by 6% (95% CI 1.05, 1.08)^[17]. Our research found that obese women were at greater risk of developing gestational diabetes than women. With normal weight we found no differences in risks between being overweight and recovering. A recent meta-analysis explored the association between GDM and BMI and estimated that the risk of GDM in overweight and obese women was 2 and 4 times that of pregnant women of normal weight. No.^[18] Although our study showed that obese women had an increased incidence of preeclampsia and GDM compared to women of normal weight due to insufficient statistical power caused by weight. At least we may not be able to detect preeclampsia in overweight and healthy women. The incidence of before and GDM is not very clear. The number of overweight and obese women^[19] compared with women with normal BMI in our study found that the incidence of prenatal medical complications in overweight and obese mothers increased. Increasing, leading to an increase in the rate of induced birth Overweight and obese mothers were more likely to have an emergency caesarean section due to indications such as preeclampsia, preeclampsia, and being unable to continue^[21] as reported in prior studies^[14]. We did not find an increase in the cerebellum ratio (CPD) in overweight and obese mothers. CPD in overweight and obese patients has been described as a consequence of size. Increased fetal and soft tissue conditions were due to the accumulation of adipose tissue in the pelvis of pregnant women [22-25], although the sample size of this study was too small to assess the effect of the index. Increased body mass on the rare outcome But we also used a mixed endpoint for severe maternal and infant outcomes including venous thromboembolism, chorioamnionitis, NICU admission rates.

Neonatal mortality, stillbirth and infant mortality. Our study found no statistically significant difference in this mixed endpoint. However, previous studies have shown an increase in mortality and morbidity among overweight and

obese mothers^[29-30]. Our study found no association between increased BMI and miscarriage. This association was previously discovered and believed to be due to early induction and a higher incidence of premature membrane rupture (PPROM).

Conclusions and results

Our findings add to the emerging literature on the consequences of maternal overweight and obesity during pregnancy and childbirth. The increase in maternal and neonatal morbidity has led to increased resource use, which has cost the community a lot. There is an urgent need to formulate an effective prevention strategy based on evidence of high-quality randomized controlled trials. Pre- and during pregnancy studies can be performed. Of the 1661 women, 43% in total were overweight or obese. Obese women were at high risk for preeclampsia (relative risk (RR) 2.99 [95% confidence interval (CI) 1.88, 4.73], $p < 0.0001$) and gestational diabetes (RR 2.10 [95% CI] 1.17, 3.79], $p = 0.01$) compared with women with normal body mass index. Compared to women with normal BMI, obese and overweight women were more likely to develop a caesarean section (induced-RR 1.33 [95% CI 1.13, 1.57], $p = 0.001$, and 1.78 [95% CI] 1.51, 2.09], $p < 0.0001$, caesarean section -RR 1.42 [95% CI 1.18, 1.70], $p = 0.0002$ and 1.63 [95% CI 1.34, 1.99], $p < 0.0001$) Female gestational age. The obesity was larger (LFGA) (RR 2.08 [95% CI 1.47, 2.93], $p < 0.0001$) and gross (RR 4.54 [95% CI 2.01, 10.24], $p =$ similar to that of normal women. Mass index of just over 0.0003). The rates of overweight and obesity in the Asia are increasing. Women who are overweight and obese are at an increased risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes. In particular, women who are obese are at an increased risk of developing gestational diabetes, gestational hypertension and preeclampsia. There is an urgent need for an effective prevention strategy.

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